

Impact of Advertising Appeals on Purchase Intention with the Mediating Role of Customer' Attitude towards Advertisement

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the impact of advertising appeals on purchase intention in the facial cream market, with particular emphasis on the mediating role of customer attitudes toward advertisements. The research focuses on three dimensions of advertising appeals: emotional appeal, rational appeal, and celebrity endorsement. A quantitative research design was employed, and data were collected from 384 respondents. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and regression techniques to test the proposed relationships.

The findings reveal that advertising appeals significantly influence customer attitudes toward advertisements, which in turn positively affect purchase intention. Importantly, customer attitude toward advertisement was identified as a key mediating variable in the relationship between advertising appeals and purchase intention. The results indicate a partial mediation effect, suggesting that advertising appeals affect purchase intention both directly and indirectly through customer attitudes.

This study offers valuable insights for cosmetic marketers by highlighting the importance of designing emotionally engaging and strategically balanced advertising messages to enhance consumer attitudes and purchase intentions. Future research could expand the study to broader geographic regions and explore similar relationships across different product categories to enhance external validity.

Keywords: Advertising Appeals, Emotional Appeal, Rational Appeal, Celebrity Endorsement, Customer Attitude toward Advertisement, Purchase Intention.

I. INTRODUCTION

I.I. Background of the study

The global cosmetics industry has experienced substantial growth in recent years, driven by increasing consumer awareness of personal care, beauty, and overall well-being. Factors such as evolving lifestyle patterns, rising disposable incomes, rapid urbanization, and the pervasive influence of digital media have significantly accelerated demand across diverse product categories. Despite economic fluctuations and market uncertainties, the cosmetics sector has consistently demonstrated resilience and adaptability. However, the outbreak of the COVID-19

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pandemic, which initially disrupted major markets in Asia, one of the leading regions in cosmetics production and consumption, had a significant impact on global supply chains, consumer purchasing behaviour, and retail operations. Consequently, key segments including personal care, hair care, body care, and skincare experienced a notable decline and required considerable time to recover. However, the post-pandemic period has shown gradual stabilization and renewed growth, highlighting the industry's capacity to adapt to shifting consumer priorities and evolving market dynamics (Roszi, Mohamad, Maryam, & Zamry, 2024).

Within this highly competitive environment, advertising plays a critical role in enabling cosmetic brands to reach and influence their target audiences. Contemporary consumers are continuously exposed to a vast volume of brand communications, making it increasingly challenging for marketers to capture attention and effectively convey brand messages. As a result, the success of advertising campaigns depends on several strategic factors, such as brand positioning, creativity, media selection, timing, and message intensity (Ganjoo, 2021).

A central component of advertising effectiveness is the advertising appeal, or message strategy, which is instrumental in attracting consumer attention, shaping brand perceptions, and influencing purchase intention. Marketing practitioners face ongoing challenges in selecting appropriate advertising appeals such as romance, humor, fear, fantasy, adventure, and emotional or rational cues to elicit desired consumer responses. The suitability of these appeals is often determined by product characteristics, brand positioning, perceived benefits, and cultural context (Zafran & Masud, 2023).

Emotional advertising appeals are particularly significant in the cosmetics industry, as consumer decisions regarding products such as facial creams are often influenced by social and psychological needs. Consumers often choose cosmetic products based on how they feel, how the product reflects their self-image, and the emotional satisfaction it gives them, rather than focusing only on the product's features or technical details. Emotional appeals, therefore, play a vital role in fulfilling psychological needs and enhancing consumer engagement (Shukor, Sulaiman, Chin, & Zakuan, 2016).

Conversely, rational advertising appeals emphasize product attributes, functional benefits, and scientific evidence, aiming to influence consumer decision-making through logical evaluation and information processing. In the skincare and cosmetics sector, such appeals often highlight efficacy, ingredients, and dermatological validation to build credibility and trust (Long, 2024).

Another widely adopted marketing communication strategy in the cosmetics industry is celebrity endorsement, which is used to enhance brand image and consumer trust. Advertisers often assume that celebrity endorsements can positively influence purchase intention, improve brand recall, and strengthen advertising effectiveness by leveraging the credibility and attractiveness of well-known personalities (Chan, Ng, Edwin K, & Luk, 2017).

Purchase intention represents the likelihood that a consumer will plan or be willing to purchase a particular product based on the alignment between product attributes and personal needs. However, it is important to note that purchase intention does not necessarily translate into actual purchase behaviour unless the consumer follows through with the decision-making process (Shukor, Sulaiman, Chin, & Zakuan, 2016).

In this context, consumers' attitudes toward advertising have been widely examined as a critical determinant of advertising effectiveness. Such attitudes reflect individuals' overall evaluations: favourable or unfavourable of advertising messages and significantly influence how consumers respond to marketing communications (Singh & Gautam, 2020). Consequently, understanding the mediating role of consumer attitudes toward advertising is essential for explaining how different advertising appeals ultimately shape purchase intention.

I.II. Problem Statement

In today's highly competitive cosmetics industry, marketers face increasing challenges in designing effective advertising strategies that can successfully influence consumer purchase intention. The proliferation of advertising messages across multiple media platforms has made it difficult for brands to capture consumer attention and create meaningful engagement. As a result, selecting the most effective advertising appeal has become a critical yet complex decision for marketers.

Despite the widespread use of emotional and rational appeals (Gokus, 2022), as well as celebrity endorsements, there is still a lack of clear understanding regarding which type of appeal is most effective in influencing consumer purchase intention in the cosmetics sector. Additionally, the mechanism through which these advertising appeals shape consumer behaviour remains insufficiently explored, particularly with regard to the role of consumers' attitudes toward advertisements.

Without a comprehensive understanding of how different advertising appeals influence purchase intention both directly and indirectly through consumer attitudes, marketers may struggle to allocate resources efficiently and design impactful campaigns. This issue is further compounded in the post-pandemic environment, where consumer preferences, media consumption habits, and purchasing behaviours have undergone significant changes.

Therefore, this study seeks to address these gaps by examining the impact of advertising appeals on purchase intention, with a specific focus on the mediating role of consumers' attitudes toward advertising in the cosmetics industry. By providing empirical evidence within a specific market context, this research aims to contribute to both academic literature and practical marketing strategies

I.III. Research Objectives

1. To examine the impact of advertising appeals on the purchase intention of facial cream
2. To examine the impact of advertising appeals on customer' attitude towards advertisement of facial cream
3. To examine the impact of customer' attitude towards advertisement on purchase intention of facial cream
4. To examine the mediating impact of customer' attitude towards advertisement between advertising appeals and Purchase intention

II. BREIF LITERATURE REVIEW AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

II.I. Advertising

Any type of paid, impersonal communication by a designated sponsor about a company, good, service, or concept is considered advertising. The term "paid" in this definition refers to the requirement that advertising space or time be purchased, with the exception of public service announcements, where media outlets contribute the space or time. Because of its impersonal nature, the advertising uses mass media (such as radio, television, magazines, and newspapers) that have the ability to reach a wide audience. Since advertising is impersonal, there is typically no chance for the recipient of the message to provide rapid reaction, with the exception of direct response marketing (Mohammednur, 2020).

Advertising is a type of communication that usually aims to convince potential consumers to buy or use more of a specific brand of good or service. It is a component of business strategies to establish, structure, and, if feasible, regulate markets, particularly for mass-produced consumer goods. The goal of many ads is to boost the consumption of those goods and services by developing and reimagining the "brand image." (Motwani, Agarwal, & Shirmali, 2014). In addition to giving businesses strong tools for brand development, market research, and independent innovation, advertising also plays a significant role in boosting brand influence, speeding up the internationalization of domestic brands, fostering the growth of related industries, increasing the effectiveness of resource allocation, encouraging the upgrading of industrial structures, and building a contemporary industrial system (Long, 2024).

II.II. Advertising Appeal

The appeal of an advertisement reflects core message behind the advertisement (Malik & Tanveer, 2018). Advertisers used advertisements with various advertising appeals to help their customers remember, recognise, and recall their brands. Meanwhile, customers' brains play an essential role in remembering, recognising, and recalling events from their daily lives. This involves remembering, identifying, and recalling brands that they saw before deciding whether or not to purchase the things they saw (Mohamad Attan, Lunyai, Ayob, & Mohd Razali, 2023).

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Advertising Appeals are powerful communication methods that capture people's attention and encourage them to acquire a specific product or service (Zhang, 2021).

The goal of advertising appeals is to change consumers' perceptions of themselves and the potential financial gain of buying a product. Consequently, the consumer's decision to buy is influenced by the message conveyed through advertising appeals. Accurate information that focuses on the features of the product is the foundation of advertising appeals. Subgroups of advertising benefits and appeals include amusement, such as humorous content and interactive games which increase consumer involvement and enjoyment, and informative content which raises product benefits and features that positively alter consumers' state of mind (Florence, Mojaye, & Lambe, 2020).

II.III. Rational Appeal

The informational or rational appeals are used to persuade customers about their product, which has a unique selling point that solves consumer problems. The purpose of informative or rational appeals is to persuade customers to purchase a specific brand. Furthermore, rational advertising appeals seek to promote information on the benefits or reasons for adopting such a product, such as the comfort, convenience, and economy that it provides. Quality, durability, efficiency, performance, dependability, and product efficacy are some of the other reasons rational advertising appeals exist. All of these rational persuasive motives are significant for customers who deliver information about various products and segments of the market (Florence, Mojaye, & Lambe, 2020).

Rational Appeals, sometimes called informative, informational, or logical appeals, rely on logic, reason, and evidence. These arguments assume that consumers make logical and reasoned conclusions during the decision-making process. Rational Appeals emphasize product benefits, quality, features, function, price, information packaging, purchase time, place, characteristics, and their efficiency (Jovanovic, Meinel, Schrodell, & Voigt, 2016).

II.IV. Emotional Appeals

Emotional Appeals aim to address consumers' psychological or social requirements. Emotional Appeals rely on appealing to customers' feelings, which can be divided into two categories: personal and social. Personal feelings include laughter, fear, love, pleasure, and happiness, whereas social-based feelings encompass status, shame, gratitude, respect, rejection, and more. Emotions can be positive or negative. Positive emotional appeals include love and comedy, negative emotional appeals elicit fear, fright, and guilt (Zhang, 2021).

In today's environment, many businesses rely on emotional appeals in their marketing to attract customers or influence purchasing decisions. Cosmetic companies, like other businesses, employ emotional appeals to entice customers to buy their products or draw their attention to a certain product. These companies use emotional appeals because they deal directly with the

consumer's feelings, which tend to psychologically stimulate the consumer by instilling emotions and feelings like happiness and joy. Believed that cosmetics marketers appeal to consumers' emotions through emotional appeals, providing them a reason to buy cosmetics. For example, they depict someone with wrinkles, pimples, or stretch marks on her face and another depiction of the same person without those ailments (Florence, Mojaye, & Lambe, 2020)

II.V. Celebrity Endorsement

Celebrities are a potent asset for marketers since they can serve as a significant reference group. Celebrities can serve as long term brand ambassadors, advocate products, or provide testimonies regarding the advantages of utilizing them (Bhatti & Fiaz, 2016). Marketers frequently select celebrity endorsers who fit the intended brand image and are also attractive, reputable, or knowledgeable. Celebrity endorsers with good looks can boost a brand's reputation and persuade customers to buy it (Hakimi, Abedniya, & Zaiem, 2011). Credible celebrities who possess pertinent expertise, experience, or information and are seen as objective can influence customers to believe statements made about a business. Customers may be more inclined to buy the promoted brand if knowledgeable and talented celebrity endorsers are seen as having experience in a certain field. Although research has indicated that celebrity trustworthiness does not increase consumers' inclination to try a brand, it is a supporting aspect that underpins source credibility. Customers want a celebrity endorser's image and the brand they are supporting to be consistent, according to research (Hakimi et al., 2011).

II.VI. Customer' Attitude towards advertisement

By establishing a link between people's thoughts and actions, perception and learning can work together to influence the development of predetermined attitudes. Since attitudes are thought to be the connection between what customers think and, eventually, what they buy, they are a crucial component of consumer theory (Terblanche-Smit, 2008)

II.VII. Cosmetic Industry

In the global cosmetics market, the skincare category now has the most market share, while the women's segment is expected to grow at the fastest rate (Roszi Naszariah Nasani Naseri et al., 2024). The study refers to cosmetics as things that beautify the skin, hair, or teeth, such as makeup, lotions, beauty creams, and scents. Some of these cosmetics include Optimal Anti-Aging Cream, Avalon Organic Cream, Dove Beauty Cream, Nivea Cream, Vaseline, Beauty Fair Body Lotion, Clear Win Soap, Skin Clear Soap, Eveeno Skin Lotion, Skin Success, Beauty Glow Cream, Johnson Cream, Johnson Body Oil, Pears Soap, Pears Oil, Dove Soap, Lux Soap, White Powder, Brown Powder, Lipsticks, and many others (Florence, Mojaye, & Lambe, 2020).

II.VIII. Purchase Intention

The idea of purchasing intention refers to consumers' propensity to actively look for relevant information and make decisions about the goods or services they want (Teng & Wang, 2015). Purchase intention is the probability that a person will carry out a specific action. Purchase intention, according to the current study, is the likelihood that a customer will make more purchases and recommend a specific cosmetics brand to others (Hsu, Chang, & chen, 2012).

(Tanjung & Hudrasyah, 2016) Define purchase intention as a person's probability of purchasing any particular product. In the typical consumer decision-making process, customers go through five stages before making a purchase decision. The following steps are problem recognition, information search, alternative evaluation, purchase decisions, and post-purchase decisions (Isamudin & Tahir Jan, 2021).

II.IX. Conceptual Framework

Three variables were conceptualised as below such as Advertising Appeal is the independent variable and Purchase Intention is the dependent variable and Customer'Attitude towards advertisement for this study purpose.

Source: Developed for Study Purpose

Following hypothesis are derived from the conceptual framework:

- H₁: Advertising Appeal has a positive impact on Purchase Intention.*
- H₂: advertising appeal has a positive impact on customer' attitude towards advertisement.*
- H₃: customer' attitude towards advertisement has a positive impact on Purchase intention*

H₄: As the mediating role customer' attitude towards advertisement has a positive impact on advertising appeal and purchase intention.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

III.I. Research approach

According to (Creswell & Creswell, 2009), research designs are strategies and processes for conducting studies that range from general hypotheses to specific techniques for gathering and analysing data. A survey questionnaire was specifically used to collect the primary data. A questionnaire, also known as a scheduled kind of measuring instrument, is a structured list of questions used to gather data from participants. Advertising Appeals, customer' attitude towards advertisements, and the context of purchase intention were measured using a five-point Likert scale, with 1 denoting "strongly disagree" and 5 denoting "strongly agree." These measurements were taken from earlier research and adapted for this study. Additionally, the surveys were created in English and translated to Sinhala and Tamil Languages. Furthermore, the questions were broken up into different portions. Section I was created to examine demographic data, such as age, gender, and educational attainment and the section II was created to evaluate respondents' general information of advertisements appeals.

III.II. Population and sampling design

According to (Creswell & Creswell, 2009) Population is the group of interest to the researcher, the group to which the researcher would like to generalize the results of the study. Consequently, This Study focuses the Consumers who are Using facial Cream in Matara District as study population.

Convenience sampling method is a non-probability Sampling technique where members of the target population who satisfy specific requirements, such as ease of access, close nearby locations, availability at a specific moment, or readiness to participate, are selected. Additionally, convenience sampling is cost-effective, and the participants are easily accessible (Mohammednur, 2020). Given the practical considerations mentioned above, the researcher decided to use the nonprobability convenience sampling method researcher has consider age group between 15-64.

III.III. Data Analysis

Measure of Reliability analysis, correlation and regression analysis were done using IBM SPSS statistics -22. Regression analysis was done to fit the model and Sobel test was used to determine the indirect effect of independent variable on dependent variable.

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IV. DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

IV.I. Correlation Analysis

The correlation coefficient is the measurement that measures the strength of the relationship between two variables and finds out the direction of the relationship (Field, Franken, Munafu, & Ingmar, 2009). In this study, correlation analysis was done to determine whether there is a relationship between independent variable and the dependent variable or not.

Table IV.I Correlations

Correlations				
		advertising appeal	Customer' attitude towards advertisement	Purchase Intention
Advertising Appeal	Pearson Correlation	1	0.655	0.787
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000	0.000
Customer' attitude towards advertisement	Pearson Correlation	0.655	1	0.722
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000		0.000
Purchase Intention	Pearson Correlation	0.787	0.722	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	
Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).				

Survey Data 2024

This correlation table shows the relationship between Advertising Appeal, Customer Attitude toward Advertisement, and Purchase Intention using Pearson correlation analysis. There is a strong positive relationship between Advertising Appeal and Customer Attitude toward Advertisement ($r = 0.655$, $p = 0.000$). This means that more appealing advertisements tend to create more positive customer attitudes. There is also a very strong positive relationship between Advertising Appeal and Purchase Intention ($r = 0.787$, $p = 0.000$). This suggests that attractive advertisements significantly increase customers' intention to purchase. Similarly, Customer Attitude toward Advertisement has a strong positive relationship with Purchase

Intention ($r = 0.722, p = 0.000$). Customers with positive attitudes toward advertisements are more likely to intend to buy the product. Since all p-values are less than 0.01, all relationships are statistically significant at the 1% level. Overall, the findings indicate that advertising appeal positively influences customer attitudes and purchase intention.

IV.II.Regression Analysis

Table IV.II: Regression Analysis between Dependent and Independent Variables

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.787	0.619	0.618	0.55047
a. Predictors: (Constant) Advertising appeal				
b. Dependent Variable : Purchase Intention				

Source: Survey data

The model summary demonstrates the impact of advertising appeal on purchase intention. The correlation coefficient (R) is 0.787 demonstrating a strong positive impact of advertising appeal on the dependent variable, purchase intention. The R square value 0.619 indicates that approximately 61.9% of the variability in consumer purchase intention can be explained by advertising appeal. The adjusted R square considers the number of predictors is 0.618. Overall results demonstrate that Advertising appeal significantly impact on purchase intention

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	187.636	1	187.636	619.229	0.000 ^b
	Residual	115.449	381	0.303		
	Total	303.086	382			
a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Intention						
b. Predictors: (Constant) Advertising appeal						

Source (Survey Data, 2024)

According to table, the ANOVA results indicate that the regression model, with Advertising Appeal as the predictor, significantly explains variations in consumer purchase intention. The regression sum of squares (187.636) indicates that advertising appeal explains a significant amount of the total variance in purchase intention, whereas the residual sum of squares (115.449) represents the variance that the model does not account for. The F-statistic (619.229) indicates that the association between advertising appeal and purchase intention is statistically significant at the $P < 0.01$ level. This high F-value suggests that the predictor (advertising appeal) has a significant effect on the dependent variable (purchase intention). In conclusion, the data demonstrates that advertising appeal significantly impact on purchase intention.

Table 4.19 Coefficient

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	0.468	0.131		3.563	0.000
	Advertising appeal	0.944	0.038	0.787	24.884	0.000

The regression results indicate that advertising appeal has a significant and positive impact on purchase intention. The unstandardized coefficient ($B = 0.944$) suggests that for every one-unit increase in advertising appeal, the dependent variable increases by 0.994 units, holding other factors constant. The standardized coefficient ($Beta = 0.787$) highlights a strong positive relationship in advertising appeal. The t-value (24.884) is large, and the associated p-value ($Sig. = 0.000$) is highly significant ($p < 0.05$) confirming the importance advertising appeal explaining variations in the dependent variable. Furthermore, the constant ($B = 0.468$) represents the baseline level of the dependent variable and is also statistically significant ($Sig. = 0.000$). These findings underline advertising appeal impact on purchase intention in facial cream products.

To identify the Impact of advertising appeals on customer' attitude towards advertisement of facial cream

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.655 ^a	.429	.427	.67885
a. Predictors: (Constant) Advertising appeal				

Source (Survey Data, 2024)

The study determines how advertising appeals affect customer' attitude toward facial cream advertisement. The R-value of 0.655 implies a moderate to strongly favorable relationship between advertising appeals and customer attitudes. This implies that as advertising appeals become more effective, customer' attitude toward advertisements improve. The R Square score of 0.429 indicates that advertising appeals account for 42.9% of the variation in customer attitudes regarding advertisements. Findings demonstrates that there is moderate Impact on advertising appeal on customer' attitude towards advertisements.

Table 4.21 Anova

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	131.726	1	131.726	285.844	.000 ^b
	Residual	175.577	381	.461		
	Total	307.303	382			
a. Dependent Variable: Customer' attitude towards advertisement						
b. Predictors: (Constant) Advertising appeal						

Source (Survey Data, 2024)

The ANOVA results reveal that the regression model, which examines the effect of advertising appeal on customer attitude toward advertisements, is statistically significant. The regression sum of squares (131.726) indicates that advertising appeal explains a significant portion of the total variance in customer attitude toward advertisements. Confirming that the advertising appeal and customer attitude is statistically significant at the P<0.01 level. Overall, the results highlight that advertising appeal has a strong and statistically significant impact on shaping customer attitudes toward advertisements.

Coefficients

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.799	.162		4.932	.000
	Advertising appeal	.791	.047	.655	16.907	.000

Source (Survey Data, 2024)

The findings indicate a considerable positive association between advertising appeal and customer attitude toward advertisements. The constant (0.799) represents a baseline positive attitude in the absence of advertising appeal, but the unstandardized coefficient shows that each one-unit increase in advertising appeal results in a 0.791 unit improvement in customer attitude. The standardized coefficient 0.655 indicates that advertisement appeal has a strong influence, as evidenced by a significant value (16.907). These findings indicate that increasing advertising appeal effectively improves customer attitudes.

To identify the Impact of customer' attitude towards advertisement on purchase intention

Model Summary

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.722 ^a	.521	.520	.61728
a. Predictors: (Constant) Customer attitude towards advertisement				

Source (Survey Data, 2024)

The model summary emphasizes the effect of customer' attitude toward advertisements on purchase intention. The R-value of 0.722 indicates a substantial positive correlation, implying that positive consumer attitudes regarding advertisements are significantly connected with increased purchase intention. With a R Square value of 0.521, buyers' views about advertisements account for 52.1% of the variance in purchase intention. The Adjusted R Square of 0.520 verifies the model's dependability by controlling for the number of predictors. The Standard Error of the Estimate (0.61728) represents the average deviation of actual values from

predicted values, indicating high predictive accuracy. Overall, the study found that customer' attitude toward advertisement are a strong predictor of purchase intention.

Anova

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	102.102	1	102.102	185.304	.000 ^b
	Residual	175.767	319	.551		
	Total	277.869	320			
a. Dependent Variable: Purchase intention						
b. Predictors: (Constant) Customer' attitude towards advertisement						

Source (Survey Data, 2024)

The ANOVA results assess the model's ability to predict purchase intention based on consumer' attitudes towards advertisement. The Regression Sum of Squares (102.102) represents the variance in purchase intention explained by the predictor. The residual sum of squares (175.767) reflects unexplained variance, whereas the total sum of squares (277.869) represents overall variance. The F-value (185.304), which is unusually high, illustrates the model's excellent explanatory power. The p-value (Sig.) of 0.000 indicates that the effect of customer attitudes on purchase intention is statistically significant. This demonstrates the importance of customer' attitude affecting purchase intention.

Coefficient

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.171	.126		9.266	.000
	Customer' attitude towards advertisement	.717	.053	.722	20.357	.000

Source (Survey Data, 2024)

The coefficients table depicts the impact of customer’ attitude towards advertisement on purchase intention. The constant (B = 1.171) represents the initial degree of purchase intention when the customer's attitude is zero. The unstandardized coefficient for customer attitude (B = 0.717) shows that for every one-unit increase in customer attitude, purchase intention rises by 0.717 units. The standardized coefficient (Beta = 0.722) indicates a high positive correlation between the two variables. The t-value (20.357) and p-value (Sig. = 0.000) show that the association is highly statistically significant. This shows that customer’ attitude towards advertisements has a positive impact on purchase intention.

To identify the mediation impact of customer’ attitude between Advertising appeals and Purchase intention

Model Summary

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.833 ^a	.694	.692	.49416
a. Predictors: (Constant) Advertising appeal, customer’ attitude towards advertisement b. Dependent variable – Purchase Intention				

Source (Survey Data, 2024)

The model summary assesses the combined impact of advertising appeals and customer attitudes towards advertisements on purchase intent. The R-value (0.833) indicates a strong positive correlation, implying that the predictors have a significant link with purchase intention. According to the R Square (0.694), advertising appeals and customer' attitude towards advertisement account for 69.4% of the variance in purchase intention. Adjusted R Square (0.692) verifies the model's dependability after accounting for the number of predictors. The Standard Error of the Estimate (0.49416) represents a low average variation between actual and anticipated values, indicating strong predictive accuracy. Overall, the model shows that advertising appeals and customer' attitudes have a considerable influence on purchase intention.

Anova

ANOVA ^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	102.102	1	102.102	185.304	.000 ^b
	Residual	175.767	319	.551		
	Total	277.869	320			
a. Dependent Variable: Purchase intention						
a. Predictors: (Constant) Advertising appeal, Customer' attitude towards advertisement						

Source (Survey Data, 2024)

The ANOVA table assesses the model's ability to predict purchase intention using advertising appeals and customer perceptions regarding advertisements. The Regression Sum of Squares (102.102) indicates the variation in purchase intention caused by the predictors, whereas the Residual Sum of Squares (175.767) represents the unexplained variation. The F-value (185.304), calculated by dividing the regression mean square by the residual mean square, is very high, showing that the model successfully accounts for the variance in purchase intention. The p-value (Sig.) of 0.000 indicates that the predictors, advertising appeals and customer attitudes, have a statistically significant effect on purchase intention.

Table 4.28 Coefficients

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.181	.122		1.488	.137
	Customer'attitude towards advertisement	.359	.037	.362	9.632	.000
	Advertising appeal	.660	.045	.550	14.646	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Purchase intention						

Source (Survey Data, 2024)

The coefficients table investigates how customer' attitude towards advertisement and advertising appeals influence purchase intention. The constant (B = 0.181) indicates the baseline purchase intention when both predictors are zero, however it is not statistically significant (p = 0.137). The unstandardized coefficient for customer attitude toward advertisements (B = 0.359) shows that a one unit increase in customer attitude boosts purchase intention by 0.359 units, with a Beta of 0.362 indicating a moderate positive effect. The unstandardized coefficient for advertising appeal (B = 0.660) demonstrates that a one unit increase in advertising appeal results in a 0.660-unit rise in purchase intention, with a Beta of

0.550, indicating a higher positive impact than customer attitude. Both predictors show statistical significance ($p = 0.000$). Advertising appeal showing a greater influence on purchase intention than customer' attitude towards advertisement.

Sobel Test

In the mediation analysis, the researcher examined the relationship between the independent variable (Advertising appeal) and the dependent variable (Purchase intention) with customer' attitude towards advertisement as the mediating variable. Following analysis describe the mediator analysis.

a= regression coefficient for the association between independent and mediator.

b= coefficient for the association between the mediator and the dependent variable.

sa= Standard error a.

sb= Standard error b.

According to the regression outputs in the current study, the following figures have to be utilized for calculating the proposed mediating effect of flow experience.

	a	b	Sa	Sb
Advertising Appeal	.0.791	.0.717	0.047	0.035

Source (Survey Data,2024)

a(sa) = B.791 se (0.047)

b(sb) = B.717 se (0.035)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	0.799	0.162		4.932	.000
	Advertising appeal	0.791	0.047	0.655	16.907	.000

Source (Survey Data,2024)

Coefficients ^a						
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Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.171	.126		9.266	.000
	Customer' attitude towards advertisement	.717	.035	.722	20.357	.000

Source (Survey Data,2024)

Variables	Sobel Test		
	Test statistics	Std. Error:	p-value
Advertising appeal	13.00412218	0.04361286	0.000

Source (Survey Data,2024)

The Sobel test showed a statistically significant mediating effect between advertising appeal and consumer purchase intention. The p- value of 0.000 indicates that the indirect effect of advertising appeal on consumer purchase intention through customer' attitude towards advertisement is statistically significant. This suggest that the impact of advertising appeal on purchase intention is not only due to direct effect but also involves an indirect impact through the mediating variable.

To determine the point estimates of the indirect effect with a statistically significant P- value in the Sobel test, the researcher calculates the unstandardized beta coefficient for the A*B.

$$\text{Point Effect} = 0.791 * 0.717 = 0.567147$$

The points effect indicate that the indirect effect quantifies how much of the independent variables impact on the dependent variable is mediated through the mediating variable. The value 0.567147 is the estimate of the indirect effect between advertising appeal and purchase intention through customer' attitude towards advertisement.

Table IV.III: Summary of Hypothesis Results

	Hypothesis	P- Value	Beta	Conclusion
H ₁	Advertising Appeal has a positive impact on Purchase Intention.	0.000	0.787	Accepted
H ₂	advertising appeal has a positive impact on customer' attitude towards advertisement.	0.000	0.655	Accepted

H ₃	customer' attitude towards advertisement has a positive impact on Purchase intention.	0.000	0.722	Accepted
H ₄	As the mediating role customer' attitude towards advertisement has a positive impact on advertising appeal and purchase intention.	0.000		Accepted

Source (Survey Data,2024)

V.I. Conclusions

The Study investigates the impact of Advertising appeals (Rational appeal, Emotional appeal, and Celebrity Endorsement) on Purchase Intention in the Facial cream market, mediated by customer' attitude towards advertisement. The study identified the gaps and emphasizing the need to explore how advertising appeals rational, emotional, and celebrity endorsement affect consumer behaviour. The study's objectives included examining direct and mediated impact between advertising appeals, customer attitudes, and purchase intention.

Literature review contextualized advertising appeals and customer attitudes as critical variables influencing purchase intention. The conceptual framework positioned advertising appeal as the independent variable, purchase intention as the dependent variable, and customer' attitude toward advertisement as a mediating variable. A quantitative approach using survey data from 383 respondents through convenience sampling method. Statistical tests, including reliability analysis, correlation, regression, and Sobel tests, were conducted using SPSS software. Research findings demonstrated that advertising appeal and customer' attitude towards advertisement has a positive impact on purchase intention. Furthermore it is showed advertising appeal (0.944) has more impact on purchase intention than customer' attitude towards advertisement (0.717) And also customer' attitude towards advertisement positive impact on advertising appeal and purchase intention. The results confirm that well-structured advertising appeals can foster favourable attitudes, enhancing purchase intentions.

V.II. Recommendations

To enhance the impact of advertising appeals on purchase intention, marketers in the facial cream market should emphasize rational appeal, emotional appeal, celebrity endorsement. For Rational appeals advertisements should clearly highlight product's features and benefits, high quality elements, emphasize the safety, demonstrating productivity. Regarding emotional appeals integrating visual elements, inspiring good music, stories, highlights family intimacy, including adventure or thrilling scene. For celebrity endorsements, selecting well aligned endorsers with attractive attributes, credibility, and expertise is crucial for building trust and brand associations. Enhancing customer' attitude towards advertisement also be a priority for

marketers, Marketers should make sure that their ads are reliable, trustworthy, entertaining, pleasing, exciting. These can be favourable impact on the attitudes and views of consumers towards advertisements. To increase purchase intention, use consistent messaging across rational, emotional, and celebrity endorsements. Efforts should be directed toward creating compelling advertisements that not only capture attention but also motivate consumers to buy and recommend products. Furthermore, businesses should constantly monitor consumer feedback to improve strategies and ensure alignment with changing consumer expectations and preferences. Advertising media is a key channel for delivering appeals and influencing customer attitudes. Focus on social media platforms like facebook, instgram, and other media are highly favoured by target audience. This study recommended to schedule evening hours (6 P.M. - 10 P.M) when engagement levels are highest.

V.III. Future Research Directions

Future research can be broaden its geographical scope to include other districts or regions, allowing for comparative analysis and generalization across Sri Lanka. Expanding the study to other cosmetic products such as skincare or healthcare items, would provide a more comprehensive understanding of advertising effectiveness. Longitudinal studies are recommended to observe how consumer attitudes and purchase intentions evolve over time. Additionally exploring the role of emerging technologies, such as AI driven personalization could reveal new opportunities for innovative advertising. Finally cross cultural studies can provide insights into the impact of sociocultural differences on the effectiveness of advertising appeals.

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